

THE ROLE OF TECHNICAL TEACHING AIDS IN DEVELOPING SPEED READING SKILLS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The development of reading skills in primary school students is considered one of the priority directions in the modern educational environment. Among these skills, speed reading holds particular significance, as it not only enables reading texts in a shorter time but also ensures rapid comprehension of information, concentration of attention, and increased reading motivation. In this regard, the integration of technical teaching aids into the learning process plays a crucial role in developing speed reading skills. Research conducted on this topic shows that interactive whiteboards, tablets, electronic textbooks, audio texts, digital reading programs, and speed reading applications have a positive impact on increasing students' reading pace while maintaining accuracy and comprehension. Thanks to technical aids, teachers can organize the reading process more flexibly, select texts appropriate to students' age and level, and provide different tasks for individual and group work. At the same time, visual and audio support elements help maintain students' attention to the text, increase their interest, and foster a positive attitude toward reading. Another advantage of technical teaching aids in speed reading instruction is the extensive feedback opportunities they provide.*

Keywords: *primary school, speed reading, reading skill, technical teaching aids, digital learning, interactive education, reading motivation*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout all stages of human societal history, humans have invented various machines and technical devices to facilitate their activities and achieve higher results with less labor and energy expenditure. The development of technology has influenced all areas of human life, including the educational and instructional process.

In the contemporary era, the rapid development of information and communication technologies (ICT) has significantly impacted all spheres of life, including the educational system. The development of speech and reading skills in primary school students, particularly the cultivation of pronunciation proficiency, constitutes one of the fundamental conditions for their successful performance in future education and social life. However, this process is not limited solely to traditional pedagogical methods; social media, television, radio, and other ICT tools also exert a direct influence on the speech and pronunciation development of young schoolchildren.

The role of ICT tools in shaping the speech culture of young children is multifaceted. Social media and interactive platforms provide students with models of correct pronunciation, while television and radio create opportunities for exposure to diverse linguistic and auditory experiences. Simultaneously, ICT tools increase students' interest in lessons by capturing their attention, make reading and speech activities interactive, and create conditions for an individualized approach.

For teachers, this situation presents both opportunities and challenges. The integration of the effectiveness of traditional teaching methods with the resources offered by ICT can render the process of improving students' pronunciation culture more efficient. This, in turn, requires primary school teachers to possess professional preparedness, creativity, and technological competencies.

In the contemporary era, the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the instructional process has become one of the most relevant directions. The emergence of teaching technology and the feasibility of its application have fundamentally transformed the learning process and introduced new approaches to teaching methodology. Whereas only a few years ago the concept of "technical aids" was primarily associated with the study of technical and exact sciences, today

there is widespread use of visual and audio resources—tape recorders, video recorders, educational films, and television programs. Teachers currently have at their disposal an extensive technical arsenal comprising various ICT systems, and the effective management of these systems requires specialized training.

Technical teaching aids constitute a collection of didactically equipped technical devices used for the presentation and processing of information in the learning and educational process. This concept encompasses two essential elements:

1. Technical devices (hardware);
2. Didactic teaching aids (information carriers), with these two elements functioning in close interrelation with one another.

Currently, as a result of the widespread application of mass media (radio, television, cinema, etc.), the transmission of information is carried out primarily in oral rather than written form. This, by enhancing the dynamism, rhythm, and pace of speech, contributes to the formation of students' rapid and expressive reading habits.

The primary purpose of ICT is to intensify the learning process, enhance its rhythm and dynamism, and contribute to the development of speech and the formation of speed reading skills. Such qualities are difficult to achieve through traditional teaching methods alone.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The use of technical aids specifically designed for instruction has opened up extensive opportunities for the creation of new teaching complexes, laboratory work, and audiovisual materials. The high effectiveness of technical aids in the educational process has been demonstrated through practical experience.

For many years, the most reliable sound technology proven through testing has been the tape recorder or tape recordings. These recordings were typically used at the initial stage of instruction. They were prepared as supplements to school textbooks, grammar, and conversation courses. Audio recordings of poems, fairy tales, plays, and songs in foreign languages were also employed for this purpose. In the contemporary era, these resources have been replaced by CD players and other digital carriers.

Thus, the integration of technical aids into the educational process plays a significant role in developing fast, conscious, and expressive reading skills in primary school students, while also creating conditions for the individualization of the learning process, increased motivation, and learning efficiency.

No single type of educational equipment, when used in isolation, can fully guarantee the success of instruction. Only the correct and purposeful combination of aids that correspond to the characteristics of the subject being studied and the cognitive activity of students enables optimal results to be achieved [2].

One of the characteristic features of the development of the modern school and pedagogy is the application of technical aids in the educational and instructional process. Technical teaching aids are considered necessary for enhancing the quality of instruction and reducing student fatigue. These aids make it possible to present educational material in a clear, vivid, and visual form, thereby rendering it more easily comprehensible and memorable.

Modern technical aids not only provide substantial assistance to the teacher but also play a crucial role in improving the quality of instruction. They contribute to the fulfillment of the following primary tasks:

- Providing students with more complete and accurate information about the phenomenon or object being studied, thereby enhancing the quality of instruction;
- Reinforcing visual teaching and consequently making accessible materials that are difficult or nearly impossible to comprehend through traditional explanatory methods (for example, a five-minute film can present complex educational material in a simple and clear format);
- Increasing the pace and rhythm of explaining educational material;
- More fully addressing students' interests and cognitive needs;

- Facilitating the work activities of both teachers and students [5].

The use of technical aids in the lesson depends on the teaching methodology chosen by the teacher. However, once these aids are incorporated into the lesson process, they actively influence the course, methodology, and overall organization of instruction.

The effective use of technical aids largely depends on the conditions in which they are applied. For example, when preparing a lesson in which video materials will be used, the teacher should first watch the video fragment carefully, review the accompanying texts, and note the parts to which students' attention should be directed.

During the film screening, the teacher should direct students' attention to key scenes and, when necessary, explain new vocabulary. If certain words and concepts used in the film are already familiar to students and their meaning can be easily understood from the context, there is no need to explain these words in advance.

Thus, the purposeful use of technical aids not only increases the effectiveness of the educational process but also creates conditions for rationally organizing the teacher's activities and maintaining students' interest and attention over extended periods.

A lesson in which technical aids are used represents a qualitatively new type of lesson. In such a lesson, the teacher must align the methodology for explaining educational material with the methods employed in television broadcasts, films, audio recordings, and other technological sources [5].

However, the characteristics of a lesson utilizing technical aids do not end there. Technical aids alter the structure and form of the lesson, making it more dynamic and interactive. Numerous observations of teachers' activities in such lessons indicate that the higher the level of a teacher's professional preparation, the more effective the application of technical aids becomes.

When planning to use technical aids, a highly qualified teacher determines in advance not only the didactic objectives but also the outcomes of applying these aids and the supplementary work to be conducted with students. The fundamental requirement is that technical aids should be employed only when necessary for achieving a specific didactic goal.

When planning a lesson in which technical aids will be used, the teacher:

- identifies the educational material that requires the use of technical aids for its study;
- selects the most appropriate teaching resource from among those available;
- plans at which stage of the lesson this resource will be used;
- pre-considers the methodology for working with the resource and its impact on students [3].

It can be said that computers are now available in almost all schools, yet they have not yet fully become an effective tool for teachers' work. Therefore, contemporary educators must learn to use computer technology as naturally as a teacher today uses a pen or chalk in the classroom.

A teacher must be proficient in information technology and purposefully apply the acquired knowledge and skills to improve teaching methodology.

Today, a computer is no longer a luxury for a teacher—it is a necessity.

Teaching children to read is, of course, challenging. However, motivating them to love reading is even more difficult. Initially, children find the reading process itself interesting [1]. They eagerly observe how familiar words are formed from letters. However, when it comes to increasing reading speed—when teachers attempt to compel reading in the classroom and parents do so at home—many children lose interest in engaging with books.

Increasingly, children prefer watching animated films of the same name instead of reading the author's original text. Watching cartoons, sitting in front of a computer, is both faster, easier, and more interesting. Children become unfamiliar with the authors, the titles of works, and their actual content; they fail to understand the differences between the author's original texts and their screen adaptations.

Reading textbooks contain virtually no information about authors, the material infrastructure of schools is outdated, it is not always possible to find a portrait of a given writer or poet, and school libraries have few books written for children.

Under such conditions, the teacher's work becomes very difficult. Each year, it becomes increasingly challenging to engage children in reading. Yet primary school students require visual

materials when learning new concepts. No matter how much we talk about books or mention their titles in class, this does not spark the same interest in primary school students as holding a book in their hands, looking through it, and reading a few sentences. However, presenting interesting facts about a writer's life creates an incentive to read their books.

It is beneficial to begin addressing these difficulties in extracurricular reading lessons. First, when preparing for a lesson, one should search for information about the author on the Internet: biographical facts, portraits, photographs. It would be more engaging to prepare presentations for lessons, sometimes incorporating documentary films or audio recordings featuring the author's voice. When lessons become more interesting for students, as they begin to become acquainted with a new author at the start of the lesson, they ask: "Who is this person? What were their interests? Are they still alive?" Initially, we invite them to make hypotheses about the person through a photograph or portrait, asking them to guess what kind of character they had. Only after students have expressed their hypotheses can we propose that they watch and listen to the materials we have found.

The difficulties associated with organizing book exhibitions have been overcome. To show children the various works of an author and different editions of the same work, it is sufficient simply to download photographs of that writer's or poet's books.

Furthermore, it is also beneficial to frequently use crossword puzzles in lesson reinforcement activities or extracurricular reading sessions. This can be either an individual task or a group activity. Creating crosswords and incorporating them into lesson presentations generates interest. Such work encourages students to read texts carefully and provides emotional motivation.

We begin preparing presentations with students starting in the second grade. By the third grade, the need arises to organize a renewed encounter with already familiar authors in a different way. For example, we can ask children what they remember from previous lessons, shifting attention from the author's personality to their books. Using materials from previous presentations, the lesson can be made more engaging and interactive.

Various techniques can be employed when working with slides: by examining text excerpts and illustrations, children identify the author's name and the title of the work. To check whether they recognize the author's books, we place books by various authors on a slide, concealing their names in advance [4]. Based solely on the book titles, children select those belonging to the same author and state the author's name.

I also provide children with opportunities to become acquainted with various interpretations of literary works: a photo album of "Artist Illustrations of the Fairy Tale," literary adaptations (screen versions), and audio recordings of musical works (both those interpreting literary works and musical pieces mentioned in the works). We then compare these with the situations presented in the original text.

For example, when working with the "Book of Dede Korkut" epic in an extracurricular reading lesson, I show children a fragment of the Azerbaijani animated film "Koroghlu" and propose that they compare it with the corresponding sections of the book. Children observe that the screen adaptation and the literary text differ:

- The animated film does not show how the heroes plan events and make decisions;
- The dialogues added in the animated film were created solely by the screenwriter, whereas the original text of the work differs;
- In the animated film, the hero Koroghlu performs certain tasks himself, but in the book, other characters carry out those tasks. For example, in the book, Girmizi Gorxmaz teaches the care and training of the horse, but in the animated film, Koroghlu does this himself: "He was training the red steed, bringing water from the woods, giving instructions to his companions..."

Thus, by observing the differences between screen adaptations and literary texts, children begin to better understand the content of the original work and the author's style.

The approach to extracurricular reading lessons using ICT yields positive results: each lesson creates emotional motivation for children; solving crossword puzzles encourages students to read literary texts carefully; students' reading horizons expand; students themselves seek out and read

works by other authors; they prepare presentations about authors' lives and works together with their parents; they select fragments from animated films; and so on.

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The approach to extracurricular reading lessons using ICT yields positive results: each lesson creates emotional motivation for children; solving crossword puzzles encourages students to read literary texts carefully; students' reading horizons expand; students themselves seek out and read works by other authors; they prepare presentations about authors' lives and works together with their parents; they select fragments from animated films; and so on [7].

Working with books is rich and diverse in both form and content. It is the duty of every educator to teach children to love books, to help them feel the need for books, and to assist them in understanding their value. In this endeavor, ICT tools serve as true helpers. Although this work is very challenging, it is extremely important and must be carried out systematically. Upon this depends what kind of readers children will grow up to be in the future and what kind of people they will become.

This is affirmed by the words of A.N. Tolstoy: "You cannot force a reader to understand the world by boring them. Reading must be interesting."

CONCLUSION

The conducted research has demonstrated that the influence of the primary school teacher on students' pronunciation culture through ICT (social media, television, radio, and other information and communication tools) is significant and multifaceted. The increasing role of ICT in the daily lives of modern children both creates incentives and presents certain challenges for the formation of their speech skills. In this regard, the teacher's activity and their correct and purposeful use of ICT play a decisive role in the development of pronunciation culture.

Based on the research findings, the application of ICT tools provides the following advantages:

1. Increases students' interest in and attention to lessons, encouraging their interactive and practical activity;
2. Accelerates the development of pronunciation and speech skills, creating conditions for the correct acquisition of sounds and clarity of speech;
3. Strengthens children's self-expression and speech independence, ensuring their active participation in the learning process;
4. Enables the teacher to implement an individualized approach, taking into account students' different levels;
5. Makes learning more comprehensible and engaging through the presentation of required lesson materials in visual and audio formats.

The research also showed that the effective use of ICT is closely linked to the teacher's professional preparation. The teacher should not merely present technical aids but must also plan their purposeful application and adapt the lesson structure and content to the possibilities offered by ICT.

Thus, the primary school teacher's use of ICT is an effective means for developing young students' pronunciation culture. This significantly contributes to the quality formation of students' speech and reading skills and has an important impact on their intellectual, aesthetic, and communicative development. In the future, the systematic integration of teachers' use of ICT into instructional strategies, as well as the development of innovative methodologies, could further enhance the effectiveness of this process.

The application of various technical teaching aids in the lesson increases the quality of education; they are used not only for the presentation of knowledge but also for its verification, reinforcement, repetition, and generalization, thus fulfilling all didactic functions. Technical aids in the lesson arouse students' interest in learning.

The effectiveness of ICT use depends on the teacher's professional preparation. A teacher preparing to conduct a lesson using technical aids must prepare the lesson carefully.

The modern world is filled with information flows. To avoid drowning in this sea of information and to correctly perform practical tasks, humans need computers to assist them. Our children's "tomorrow" is the information society. It is important to learn to use computers, to collect and systematize information, and to extract the necessary data. Thanks to computers, it is possible to increase vocabulary in a short time, develop grammatical structure, fill gaps in the phonetic development of speech, develop coherent speech, and enhance writing attention, which leads to improved literacy. Students' interest in the learning process increases, and their skills in self-assessment and independent activity develop.

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